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Challenges in the Curriculum Development Steps to Collaborative Teaching

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ABSTRACT

The engineers need not only good knowledge of their special technical field but also e.g. social, analytical thinking, problem solving and language skills. Especially knowing how to learn and adopt new and how to combine their own knowledge with other specialists is important. All these require consideration when reforming the new curricula. This article describes the process of the curriculum development in the Mechanical Engineering Education.

The new curriculum is based on competence and problem-based learning. This new curriculum challenges the teachers to be more like counsellors in the students' learning processes. This new curriculum also motivates the teachers of different subjects to cooperate and teach together with each other. This makes the teachers plan, check, guide and assess the courses together. Competency-based curriculum considers the students more as individuals than as groups and this requires the students to be more active in their learning process.

In the department of Mechanical Engineering, the new curriculum consists of the academic year and semester themes. The academic year themes are *Learning about Work of Mechanical Engineers*, *Engineer's Toolbox*, *Creative Engineers* and *Pre-Engineers*. Every semester has a CDIO-type semester project course and all the other courses support this project course.

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INTRODUCTION

The development of the curriculums is a challenging and time-consuming process. How to anticipate, what kind of competence is needed in the working life in the future? The operational environment is changing so fast that it is hard for the educators to keep up with it. In different education fields, there are permanent topics in engineering education; it is necessary to teach natural sciences and selected subjects of the technical field but also social skills, analytical thinking skills, problem solving skills, language skills are needed in the working life. The students must know how they learn and adopt new and how they can combine their own knowledge with other students.

The new curricula of Lapland University of Applied Sciences are based on competence and problem-based learning. These new curricula challenge the teachers to be more like counsellors, not traditional teachers in the students' learning processes. These new curricula also motivate the teachers of different subjects to cooperate and teach together with each other; every course has to have more than two teachers. Competency-based curriculum considers the students more as individuals than as groups. These new curricula also require the students to be more active in their learning processes and this has to be emphasized and taught to the students.

The engineering education is not the most popular subject to study nowadays. If the students are not committed to the subjects they are studying, or they do not know what kind of work the engineers do, they may not be so motivated to study and they may drop out their studies. The thread of the mechanical engineering competence was in the center when the new curriculum of the Mechanical Engineering Education was reformed. The new curricula will be introduced in the fall 2017.

1 GENERAL

Lapland University of Applied Sciences (later LUAS) started at the beginning of 2014. Two different Universities of Applied Sciences (Rovaniemi University of Applied Sciences and Kemi-Tornio University of Applied Sciences) merged and it was necessary to start pedagogical development and combine different practises. One of the important tasks was to reform the curricula of the different degree programmes. The content of the European Bologna Process and the funding model of the Finnish Ministry of Education for the Finnish universities and universities of applied sciences also influenced the curriculum development and reform. The operation environment and working life expect from the future employees that they are able to learn by themselves, together and from each other and they can build new information combining their own knowledge with other specialists. The target of the new curriculum is to confirm a creative and learner-centered culture of learning. Fragmentary courses are integrated into larger modules and students together process the phenomena and problems of the working life.

The aim of the problem-based learning is to increase creativeness and communality in the students learning process. The individual students study as active team members

resolving learning problems. The alternative proposition of the solutions expand the students' individual knowledge. The target of organizing the learning is to reduce teacher-centered teaching and increase work-oriented learning. The essential themes are interaction and co-operation between the students, communal learning, the guidance of the learning, invocation of the group dynamics in the learning process and developing evaluation.

The old curricula of the different education programmes are usually separate 3 credit courses including general studies, professional studies and line specific studies but they are rarely connected with each other; only some courses. This may produce some disruption in the students learning process where they do not see the meaning of learning of these different skills and the motivation of performing these courses may not be so high. With the new curriculum, these separate courses vanish or are reduced. In the curriculum of the engineering programmes, e.g. the general studies are connected more tightly to professional studies. The thread of the courses in the whole degree is more clear to the students, which may also enhance the study progress and reduce drop-outs.

Project-based learning is applied in the curricula of different engineering programmes. This new curriculum challenges the teachers to be more like instructors, not traditional teachers in the students' learning processes. The teachers have to learn a new role and instruct the students in their learning process and task. Instead of giving a lecture, the teacher introduces a problem and the students search for information and try to solve the problem. Therefore, information retrieval is essential in the learning process. This new curriculum gives the teachers of different subject the possibility to cooperate and teach together with each other. In this way, the individual teachers really get better overview of the education and have an insight into different subjects. Therefore, the integration between different subjects deepens. Earlier the teachers liked to teach alone so that the doors of the classrooms were closed and every teacher could give best information with his/her own individual expertise. The team teaching is the cornerstone of operations in the competence-based curricula. The team teachers plan, teach and assess the pedagogic learning process together. It is not easy for a teacher to change his/her teaching method to competence and problem-based one and act more like counsellor. In the curriculum process of the LUAS, there were quite many events and education session for the teachers on competence and problem-based learning and team teaching so everybody knew what that means in their own teaching. The students are not familiar with this kind of teaching method and that is why the teachers have to introduce the new curriculum to the students and explain the working method and assessments of the courses. Emphasising a student-centred approach will also speed up studies. In addition, recognition of prior learning will be improved, and work life orientation and teaching of entrepreneurial skills will be increased.

2 PROCESS OF THE CURRICULUM DEVELOPMENT

At the beginning, there were quite many events and education sessions to the teachers on competence and problem-based learning and team teaching in the curriculum process of the LUAS. Some of the events were hold to the entire staff together; some events were hold to the different educations (e.g. engineering education) only. This was a major investment of time and money from the LUAS to improve the teachers' competence of the new curriculum. All of these events also improved mutual work where different teachers of the education shared their expertise.

In every education programme, a teacher was named as a person in charge of the curriculum. These persons (in charge of curriculum) led and coordinated the work of the curriculum development in the education programmes. They had several meetings together regularly and shared each other the current phase of the curriculum development process of different education programmes. New information and practices were rapidly used in the development processes of the curricula. These kinds of activities also increased shared expertise inside the education programmes.

2.1 On the way to the new curriculum of Mechanical Engineering

Bachelor of Engineering studies take four years to complete containing 240 ECTS credits. The structure of the Mechanical Engineer curriculum consists basic and professional studies 180 ECTS (basic studies (50 ECTS) and professional studies (130 ECTS)), elective studies 15 ECTS, practical training 30 ECTS and thesis 15 ECTS. First, the teachers, students, representatives of the surrounding industry, co-operative companies and other important partners, e.g. research groups, were asked to specify the competences of the mechanical engineers. A lot of time was spent on this work but it was also interesting and rewarding to analyse and anticipate the skills the future mechanical engineers need in the changing working life.

The new curriculum of Mechanical Engineering was created from a “blank slate” and it consists of projects and various study modules reflecting the competences. The names of these projects and study modules are inspiring and modern and try to illustrate better the theme of the academic year to the students. The competence of the Mechanical Engineering is based on the contents of the projects and the aim of the know-how of the study modules. The professional growth of the mechanical engineers proceeds gradually from the first academic year to the last year in every academic year and semester themes.

The learning and/or problem-based project is in the center of every semesters theme. The contents of the different study modules are integrated into the content of the semester project. The competence of the student is based on these semester themes. Figure 1 presents an example of a semester project, and how the study modules support this.

Fig. 1. An example of the semester theme.

In the region of Lapland, there are steel, paper, energy and mining companies and their needs of the future professionals were taken into consideration when determining these alternative professional studies. It is also important that there are possibilities to gain academic competence in the region. The people who live in the region are used

to long distances of the services and art condition. In the Mechanical Engineering education in the new curriculum, there are three different kinds of alternative professional study options and the students choose one of them in the third academic year. These alternative professional studies are: Industrial Professional, Product Development Professional and Mining Professional. All of these alternative professional studies contain semester projects, mandatory courses and optional courses. Figure 2 presents the description of these alternative studies.

Fig. 2. Alternative studies of the Mechanical Engineering

3 EXPERIENCES OF THE COLLABORATIVE CURRICULUM PLANNING

In the department of Mechanical Engineering, the academic year consists of the semester themes. The academic years have the following themes *Learning about Work of Mechanical Engineers*, *Engineer's Toolbox*, *Creative Engineers* and *Pre-Engineers*. Every semester has a semester project course and all the other courses support this project course. These semester projects are like CDIO projects (Conceive-Design-Implement-Operate). The professional competence is developed by active learning and supervision methods.

The same curriculum is applied in young and in adult education, only some of the vocational subject studies are compensated with practical training. The students in adult education study in the evenings and on Saturdays, and so the number of contact lessons is smaller and this sets its own demands and restrictions in the teaching methods as well as in the curriculum. The students must be self-directive in order to manage their studies along with their work and private lives. The teaching methods can consist of e.g. flipped classroom, simulation, online teaching and independent studies.

Table 1 presents an example of the content of one academic year (first academic year). The first year is critical for the students if they are not motivated and they do not recognise and understand the professional field of the studies. Therefore, they are possible dropouts. In the new curriculum of Mechanical Engineering, there are many studies where the engineering work and working environments are demonstrated with basic and professional studies. In the old curriculum of the Mechanical Engineering, the basic, professional and elective courses were mainly 3 ETCS. The basic courses consisted of maths, physics, language, communication and learning skills. The

professional courses consisted of different kinds of sections of Mechanical Engineering.

Table 1. An example of the content of the Academic Year.

1. Academic Year					
Academic Year Theme	Semester Theme	Study Module	Extent	Responsible Teacher	Other Teachers
Learning about Work of Mechanical Engineers	On the Way to Becoming an Engineer	Project: Familiarization with Arctic Working Environment	5	N.N.	A.A., B.B., C.C.
		Perspective on Work of Engineers	5	N.N.	A.A., B.B., C.C.
		Natural Sciences of Engineers	5	N.N.	D.D.
		Tools and Software of Learning	5	N.N.	E.E.
		The basic of Technical Design	5	N.N.	
		Basics of Industrial Engineering	5	N.N.	F.F.
	Language of Engineers	Project: How to Use the Tools of Engineers	5	N.N.	A.A., B.B., C.C.
		Tools of Mathematics and Physics	5	N.N.	G.G.
		Basic of Mechanical Engineering	5	N.N.	A.A., B.B., C.C.
		Manufacturing Processes and Material Science	5	N.N.	
		Basics of Technical Mechanics	5	N.N.	
		Projects and Workshops	5	N.N.	A.A., B.B.

The engineers need not only good knowledge of their special technical field but also e.g. social skills, analytical thinking skills, problem solving skills, language skills. Especially knowing how to learn and adopt new and how to combine their own knowledge with other specialists is important. All these require consideration when drawing up the new curricula. In the process of the curriculum development, a lot of effort was put when considering the themes and names of the semesters. It is necessary that students, mainly young people, understand what they study and what kind of competence they achieve. It is also important that all this is presented in "young people's language". The academic year and semester themes also portray well the idea of Mechanical Engineering studies.

In the first academic year, the field of Mechanical Engineering becomes familiar to the students. They practise basic subjects of the Mechanical Engineering combined to the natural science, language and social skill studies. In the second academic year the basic tools of the Mechanical Engineering become more familiar and the students learn how to apply all the knowledge they have achieved. The students also can work on the projects and they can apply different kinds of problem-based methods. In the third academic year, the students can together solve real working life problems. In the last academic year, the students deepen the Mechanical Engineering competence and at

the end of the year they will graduate. The students can work in different kinds of Mechanical Engineering jobs, they manage in different situations and they can be supervisors.

At this phase of the curriculum process, the timetables for the autumn semester are being drawn up. The challenge is to combine the timetable of new curriculum and the old curriculum.

4 SUMMARY

The process have been long and it has taken much time to plan the curriculum together. Drawing up the timetables is challenging because you have to take into consideration the daytime and the adult students, studying according to the new curriculum and the old one.

The assessment of the courses or projects will give new challenges to the teachers, because it is based on continuous learning and the learning process of students and it will be done together with several teachers. On the other hand, the assessment is viewed from different perspectives and this is advantageous to the students. The challenge of the curriculum development processes is that the advantages and disadvantages will be seen when the first students graduate. Time will show.

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